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List of abbreviations

CLP	<i>Classification, Labelling and Packaging</i>
EC	<i>European Commission</i>
ECHA	<i>European Chemical Agency</i>
ED HH	<i>Endocrine Disruptor for Human Health</i>
ED ENV	<i>Endocrine Disruptor for Environment</i>
GHS	<i>Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals</i>
IAS	<i>Intended Added Substances</i>
JRC	<i>Joint Research Centre</i>
LCA	<i>Life Cycle Assessment</i>
LCC	<i>Life Cycle Costing</i>
LLNA	<i>Local Lymph Node Assay</i>
NIAS	<i>Non-Intended Added Substances</i>
OECD	<i>Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development</i>
PBT/vPvB	<i>Persistent, Bioaccumulative and Toxic / very Persistent and very Bioaccumulative</i>
PHBV	<i>Poly -hydroxybutyrate – co- -hydroxy valerate</i>
QSAR	<i>Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship</i>
REACH	<i>Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals</i>
RMM	<i>Risk Management Measures</i>
So-LCA	<i>Social-Life Cycle Assessment</i>
STOT-RE	<i>Specific Target Organ Toxicity - Repeated Exposure</i>
STOT-SE	<i>Specific Target Organ Toxicity - Single Exposure</i>
SVHC	<i>Substances of Very High Concern</i>
SVOCs	<i>Semi-volatile organic compounds</i>
TG	<i>Test Guideline</i>
VOCs	<i>Volatile Organic Compounds</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>

1. Executive Summary

This report, Deliverable 6.6, provides a comprehensive overview of the initial hazard and risk assessment of materials utilized during the first 18 months of the project. ViSS Framework for Safety by Design Assessment, as detailed in Deliverable 6.3, is applied to evaluate the safety profiles of materials in use.

Key to this process, Intended Added Substances (IAS) have been compiled from work packages WP1 and WP2. These substances were methodically assessed using the ViSS SSbD Framework's scoring system, collecting available data from public databases to calculate their intrinsic properties systematically.

Furthermore, the deliverable details the early-stage development of Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) models. These models are designed to specifically address the assessment of Non-Intended Added Substances (NIAS), utilizing the same public data sources for a robust analysis.

While deliverable 6.6 explains the preliminary steps and methodologies adopted for SSbD, the ongoing work and anticipated results will be detailed in the next Safety Report (Deliverable 6.9).

For version 2.0 of Deliverable 6.6, several small changes were made based on reviewer comments:

- An annex has been included at the end of this document containing the questionnaires and chemical inventory done for SSbD assessment, including questions and answers. However, considering the sensitive information included, the use of broader terms has still been used for keeping confidentiality, since this deliverable is classified as "Public".
- Regarding the use of broader terms in additives, a reminder to consult the Deliverable 1.5 for chemical information about additives has been mentioned.
- A minor clarification has been added for endpoint classification in hazard assessment of additives. This information is also explained in the introduction section.
- Detailed information has been included in the assessment of the toxicological profile of PHBV, specifying the next steps for addressing their potential hazards from a multidimensional approach.
- Finally, typos and formatting errors have been corrected.

2. Introduction

a. ViSS SSbD Framework

In Deliverable 6.3 a score-system methodology is presented for ViSS SSbD framework construction and assessment. In this methodology, a score-system is proposed (from 0 to 4) for each indicator of every aspect (Figure 1). This score system has a cut-off threshold, and scores from 0 to 1 will not pass the minimum criteria. Therefore, each dimension (Safety, LCA, So-LCA and LCC) will be independently evaluated according to their indicators.

For Safety, the proposed categories and their indicators are gathered in Table 1. These indicators have been collected from European Commission (EC) SSbD framework and GHS (Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals).

Figure 1 - ViSS SSbD framework construction and assessment: methodology (example of assessment)

Table 1 - Safety hazards

Categories	Indicators
Health hazards	Acute Toxicity (Oral/Dermal/Inhalation)
	Skin Corrosion/Irritation
	Serious Eye Damage/Eye Irritation
	Respiratory or Skin Sensitization (including allergy) ²
	Germ Cell Mutagenicity
	Carcinogenicity
	Reproductive Toxicology
	Target Organ Systemic Toxicity - Single Exposure
	Target Organ Systemic Toxicity - Repeated Exposure
	Aspiration toxicity
Environmental hazards	Hazardous to Aquatic Environment (Acute/Chronic)
	Hazardous to the ozone layer
	Persistence of the Hazards ³

The score from 0 to 4 for failing or passing the criteria (Table 2) is extracted from *Framework for the definition of criteria and evaluation procedure for chemicals and materials (European Commission, 2022)*^j for evaluation system of Environmental sustainability.

Table 2 - Evaluation system for environmental sustainability assessment

Position to reference	Score	Colour code	
No improvement	0		Fail the criteria
Improvement + 5%	1		
Improvement + 5% to 20%	2		Pass the criteria
Improvement + 20% to 40%	3		
Improvement > 40%	4		

However, ‘position to reference’ to evaluate safety dimension does not make sense, because there is no standardized benchmark to perform a comparative assessment to know the improvement of safety regarding different safe-by-design strategies. Actually, there is a specific score-system assigned to safety dimensions to be comparable to other three dimensions.

Figure 2 - Workflow for assessing intrinsic properties

Figure 2 shows the proposed workflow for evaluating criteria of intrinsic properties of materials in safety dimension. A cut-off criterion is also applied; hence, Table 3 shows the equivalence between ViSS score-system and Safety Criteria.

Table 3 - Equivalence between Score-system and intrinsic properties assessment

Score	Hazard assessment
4	Safe (Level 3)
3	Not pass criteria H3 (Level 2)
2	Not pass criteria H2 (Level 1)
1	Not pass criteria H1 (Level 0)
0	No data

In the SSbD frameworkⁱ, criterion H1 is defined as:

“The criterion refers to the most harmful substances, according to CSS, including the Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC) according to REACH Art. 57(a-f) and additional hazard properties.

This is a cut-off criterion, establishing a minimum set of hazard requirements that need to be fulfilled by a chemical or material in order to be considered eventually SSbD after the other assessments are performed.

Therefore, the assessment of the other aspects can be performed in order to understand the overall SSbD performance (e.g. safety during the use assessed in Step 3, other environmental sustainability aspects assessed in Step 4) if this helps the innovation process”.

In addition, the SSbD framework establishes that the chemicals and materials which do not pass this criterion should be:

- Prioritized for substitution
- Re-designed in order to reduce their adverse effects

- Only allowed in uses proven essential for society (e.g. if their use is necessary for health, safety or is critical for the functioning of society and if there are no alternatives that are acceptable from the standpoint of environment and health)
- Safely used and emissions/exposure be controlled along the whole life cycle while activities are undertaken to develop alternatives as soon as possible and their use is phased out as soon as less hazardous alternatives are available
- Tracked through their life cycle

Criteria H1-H2-H3 regarding endpoint classification of indicators can be found in Figure 3. (extracted from SSbD Framework). According to this categorization, we can assign a score for each category of every endpoint. In addition, categories are well-known for commercial products because of *Classification, Labelling and Packaging* (CLP) Regulation ((EC) No 1272/2008)ⁱⁱ. Every indicator can be evaluated regarding data for experimental assays. In Chapter R.7a of *Guidance on Information Requirements and Chemical Safety Assessment*ⁱⁱⁱ we can find the categorization criteria for each endpoint, with quantitative threshold for in vivo or in vitro data, and the level of evidence for human data that is needed to classify them.

Group definition	Human health hazards	Environmental hazards	Physical hazards
Includes the <u>most harmful substances</u> (according to CSS (EC, 2020a)), including the <u>substances of very high concern</u> (SVHC) according to REACH Art. 57(a-f) ^{20,21} (EU, 2006). These hazard properties form <u>Criterion H1</u> .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carcinogenicity Cat. 1A and 1B • Germ cell mutagenicity Cat. 1A and 1B • Reproductive / developmental toxicity Cat. 1A and 1B • Endocrine disruption Cat. 1 (human health) • Respiratory sensitisation Cat. 1 • Specific target organ toxicity - repeated exposure (STOT-RE) Cat. 1, including immunotoxicity and neurotoxicity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic / very persistent and very bioaccumulative (PBT/vPvB) • Persistent, mobile and toxic / very persistent and mobile (PMT/vPvM) • Endocrine disruption Cat. 1 (environment) 	
Includes <u>substances of concern</u> , as described in CSS (EC, 2020a), defined in the Article 2(28) of SPI proposal (EC, 2022b) ²² and that are not already included in Criterion H1. These hazard properties form <u>Criterion H2</u> .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skin sensitisation Cat. 1 • Carcinogenicity Cat. 2 • Germ cell mutagenicity Cat. 2 • Reproductive / developmental toxicity Cat. 2 • Specific target organ toxicity - repeated exposure (STOT-RE) Cat. 2 • Specific target organ toxicity - single exposure (STOT-SE) Cat. 1 and 2 • Endocrine disruption Cat. 2 (human health) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hazardous for the ozone layer • Chronic environmental toxicity (chronic aquatic toxicity) • Endocrine disruption Cat. 2 (environment) 	
Includes the <u>other hazard classes</u> not part already in Criteria H1 and H2. These hazard properties form <u>Criterion H3</u> .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acute toxicity • Skin corrosion • Skin irritation • Serious eye damage/eye irritation • Aspiration hazard (Cat. 1) • Specific target organ toxicity - single exposure (STOT-SE) Cat. 3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acute environmental toxicity (acute aquatic toxicity) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explosives • Flammable gases, liquids and solids • Aerosols • Oxidising gases, liquids, solids • Gases under pressure • Self-reactive • Pyrophoric liquids, solid • Self-heating • In contact with water emits flammable gas • Organic peroxides • Corrosivity • Desensitised explosives

Figure 3 - List of indicators (hazard properties) relevant for Safety Dimension

The main way to assess aspects of safety dimension is to use the categorization of endpoints according to CLP regulation and the subsequent workflow for intrinsic properties of SSbD assessment.

In Table 4, every endpoint is categorized regarding their safety level. Of each category, a score has been assigned based on ViSS Score-system. This table is a practical application of the Figure 3 with the score-system proposed for ViSS in D6.3, explained in Table 2.

Table 4 - Endpoint Score-system based on CLP Categorization

	Aspect	Indicator	Endpoint	Category	Score
SAFETY	Health hazards	Toxicity	Acute Toxicity	Category 1	3
				Category 2	3
				Category 3	3
				Category 4	3
			Reproductive Toxicology	Category 1	1
				Category 2	2
			STOT-SE	Category 1	2
				Category 2	2
				Category 3	3
			STOR-RE	Category 1	1
				Category 2	2
			Aspiration hazard	Category 1	3
		Corrosion and Irritation	Skin Corrosion/Irritation	Category 1	3
				Category 2	3
			Serious Eye Damage/Eye Irritation	Category 1	3
				Category 2	3
		Sensitization	Respiratory or Skin Sensitization (including allergy)	Respiratory Sensitization Category 1	1
				Skin Sensitization Category 1	2
	Mutagenicity	Germ Cell Mutagenicity	Category 1	1	
			Category 2	2	
	Carcinogenicity	Carcinogenicity	Category 1	1	
			Category 2	2	
	Environmental hazards	Aquatic environment	Hazardous to Aquatic Environment (Acute/Chronic)	Chronic Toxicity	2
				Acute Toxicity	3
Ozone layer		Hazardous to the ozone layer	Category 1	2	
Persistence of the hazards	Persistence of the Hazards	PBT/vPvB	1		

b. SSbD contribution for WP1

The goals of WP1 are

- To define the technical specifications of the ViSS feedstocks, materials and products along the value chain.
- Perform a management plan for collecting the residues to be used as feedstocks for PHBV production, formulation and compounding.

- To identify potential residues variability and to apply an appropriate pre-treatment under ViSS SSbD criteria (defined in WP6) to reach the relevant properties providing a homogeneous feedstock.
- Selecting the optimal additives based on ViSS SSbD criteria.

To guarantee the consecution of the planned goals, the contribution of WP6 is fundamental. Especially, the contribution of Task 6.3 for the selection of optimal additives.

Figure 4 depicts the timeline and deadlines for WP6 and their connection with WP1 and, specifically, Task 1.4 which is the target of the SSbD assessment. Once Deliverable 1.5 was submitted, we were able to proceed with the safety workflow and safety assessment of proposed additives.

Figure 4 - Expected schedule for WP6 contribution to WP1

c. SSbD contribution for WP2

The main goal of the WP2 is to optimize the upstream and downstream processes at pilot scale to maximize the PHBV range production as baseline for the demo plant. Therefore, all the developments will be continuously assessed under the SSbD criteria, carried out in parallel through WP6.

In Figure 5, we have depicted the WP6 timeline including WP2 contributions and deadlines.

In Deliverable 6.6, we have performed the first step of the SSbD Assessment: Toxicological study of the intrinsic properties of the raw materials used in WP2. For the contribution referring to safety assessment related with exposure (Step 2 -Processing- and Step 3 -Environment-), it will be included in deliverable 6.9. However, earlier work is expected to be done, especially for giving some feedback before the later scale-up and demo-plant building.

Figure 5 - Expected schedule for WP6 contribution to WP2

3. Methodology: Databases for SSbD Assessment

a. Data Collection of IAS

Additives from Deliverable 1.5

The first approach of the SSbD assessment was to collect all available data from public resources to know the current knowledge about the safety and potential hazards of chemicals.

Deliverable 1.5. describes the work carried out in ViSS WP1 Task 1.4 Optimization of PHBV property modifiers and its conclusions regarding additive selection and optimal PHBV formulation. It reports the pre-selection of biobased additives to be considered in ViSS. The selection is based on existing experimental results, theoretical considerations and SSbD criteria adopted in the project (Deliverable 6.3).

Following the indications given by the EC Joint Research Centre (JRC), which is the leading institution in the development of the SSbD approach, based on existing experimental results, theoretical considerations and SSbD principles, saccharides, polyphenols and other additives were selected as inexpensive and non-toxic/GRAS additives to be considered for the ViSS PHBV formulations. Table 5 depicts the selected additives.

All additives are listed with broader terms to keep confidentiality of information. For this, only chemical families are listed for each additive. **For further details regarding chemical composition, please, go to Deliverable 1.5.**

- Saccharides
- Polyphenols
- Others

Table 5 - Additive molecules selected in Deliverable 1.5.

Additive	Type
Additive 1	Saccharide
Additive 2	Saccharide
Additive 3	Saccharide
Additive 4	Saccharide
Additive 5	Saccharide
Additive 6	Saccharide
Additive 7	Saccharide
Additive 8	Other
Additive 9	Other
Additive 10	Polyphenol

Data collection of IAS: Questionnaires for WP2 partners

From IDENER some questionnaires were created to ask CETBIO, CETEC and IRIS about the chemicals used, conditions of reactions and other aspects of interest. In addition, a spreadsheet was sent to these partners as chemical inventory to collect information, CAS numbers, even Safety Datasheets and approximated amount of chemicals employed in tasks within WP2. These questionnaires can be found in the ANNEX 1 at the end of this deliverable.

Due to this report is only focus on intrinsic properties of chemicals used in the process, we limit the scope of this report to those chemicals listed in the inventory. Table 6 shows all these chemicals.

Similar to additives from WP1, chemicals are listed with broader terms to keep confidentiality of information. All partners have received an individual report for safety assessment where all hazards are evaluated for actual chemicals.

Table 6 - List of chemicals from WP2

Name
CETBIO
<i>CETBIO Buffer 1</i>
<i>CETBIO Buffer 2</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 1</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 2</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 3</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 4</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 5</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 6</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 7</i>
<i>CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 1</i>
<i>CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 2</i>
<i>CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 3</i>
<i>CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 4</i>
<i>PHBV (Final Product)</i>
CETEC
<i>CETEC Solvent 1</i>
<i>PHBV (Final Product)</i>
IRIS
<i>IRIS Additive 1</i>
<i>IRIS Buffer 1</i>
<i>IRIS Buffer 2</i>
<i>IRIS Solvent 1</i>
<i>IRIS Solvent 2</i>

b. ECHA Databases

Therefore, a total of 4 databases from the European Chemical Agency (ECHA) website were consulted to perform a whole evaluation of the H1 criterion.

These databases are:

- SVHC (Substances of Very High Concern) list.^{iv}
All substances identified as SVHC will not pass the criterion H1
- ED list: Endocrine Disruptor.^v
Substances categorized as ED HH (Endocrine Disruptor for Human Health) and ED ENV (Endocrine Disruptor for Environment) or, even, both, will not pass the criterion H1
- PBT list.^{vi}
Those substances identified as PBT (Persistence, bioaccumulation and toxicity), or vPvB (very Persistent and very Bioaccumulative), or, even, both, will not pass the criterion H1.
- CLP (H): Table of harmonized entries in Annex VI to CLP - it shall apply from 1 February 2025).^{vii}
Substances classified as 'Carc. 1', 'Muta. 1', 'Repr. 1', 'Resp. Sens. 1' and/or 'STOT RE 1' will not pass the H1 criterion. The rest of the information of CLP inventory will be employed to give a score for those substances that pass the H1 criterion.

c. Toxicological databases

In addition to data from ECHA website, an exhaustive search was performed in toxicological databases to complete the information about safety. It was focused on Cancer and Genotoxicity information because they are two of the more relevant data for human assessment, in addition to the huge amounts of data which are available.

COMPTOX database^{viii} was the chosen one for this task because some of the most important databases are included in COMPTOX Database, such as eChemPortal, TOXNET or ISHL. IDENER has developed webscraping and classification algorithms to assess the potential carcinogenicity and genotoxicity of data, always considering the endpoint classification of SSbD framework.

4. Results

a. Safety Assessment of IAS

i. Additives Assessment (WP1)

H1 Criterion

All additives passed the H1 criterion. No Cancer nor Genotoxicity conclusive assays were found as positive for the additive list members in COMPTOX database. In addition, no indication from other databases collected from ECHA's repository were found for these compounds.

Table 7 shows the absence of data for the chemicals of concern, as searches across databases have returned no results.

Table 7 - Assessment for H1 criterion

Name	ADDITIVES	Cancer COMPTOX	Genotoxicity COMPTOX	SVHC	ED HH	ED ENV	PBT	vPvB	CLP
Additive 1	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Additive 2	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Additive 3	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Additive 4	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Additive 5	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Additive 6	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Additive 7	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Additive 8	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Additive 9	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Additive 10	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No

Therefore, all chemicals can be considered for the next step (Task 3.2.2 Compounding) without any concern. Anyway, in the following section we will assess the safety profile for each individual additive in case partners from WP3 want to consider them.

Score-system profile

Considering safety score-system is based on endpoints from CLP inventory, we will use CLP harmonized classification, CLP notifications provided by companies and REACH regulation^{ix} to evaluate the current hazards of the proposed additives to generate a complete safety profile. For more information about the score system and, specifically, safety implementation, you can read again Section 1: Introduction.

Table 8 - Summary of WP1 chemical profile

	Acute Tox	Repr. Tox	STOT-SE	STOT-SE	Aspiration Tox	Skin Corrosion	Skin Irritation	Eye Dm/ Eye Irr	Resp/Skin Sens.	Mutagenicity	Carcinogenicity	Aquatic Env.	Ozone Layer	Persistence
Additive 1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Additive 2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Additive 3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Additive 4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Additive 5	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	2	4	4
Additive 6	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Additive 7	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Additive 8	4	4	4	3	4	4	3	3	2	4	4	4	4	4
Additive 9	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Additive 10	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4

For those substances with a score 4 in every column, we can assume that they are not present on the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulation. In addition, according to most notifications provided by companies to ECHA in REACH registrations and CLP notifications, no hazards have been classified. Therefore, we can tentatively consider them as safe additives with a score equal to 4 in all endpoints.

In the following paragraphs, we analyse in detailed the rest of substances with, at least, an endpoint which has been assigned with a certain hazard. It is important to highlight that because **none of these additives present a score lower than 1 for any endpoint, all of them pass the cut-off criteria and can be considered for the next steps (as it is depicted in Figure 2)**. However, for those which present a score lower than 4, special attention should be pay for the risk management strategy, considering their benefits versus the inherent hazards.

Additive 5 (Figure 6)

According to the classification provided by companies to ECHA in REACH registrations this substance causes serious eye irritation (H319). Eye irritation is classified in H3 Criteria and, therefore, it would be classified as Level 2 and its score is 3.

In addition, according to the classification provided by companies to ECHA in CLP notifications, Additive 5 can be considered as Hazardous for the environment (Chronic Toxicity, Category 3 (H412)). This endpoint is part of Criterion H2, hence it will be classified in level 1 with a score of 2.

This additive can still be considered for the compounding; however, its selection implies a subsequent specific risk management strategy.

Figure 6 – Additive 5 score system

Additive 8 (Figure 7)

Additive 8 is not on the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulations.

However, according to the classification provided by companies in CLP notifications this substance causes serious eye irritation (H319), skin irritation (H315), may cause respiratory irritation (H335) and may cause an allergic skin reaction (H317).

Eye irritation, skin irritation and respiratory irritation (STOT-RE, Category 3) are part of the H3 Criteria and, therefore, they will have a score of 3. Meanwhile, allergic reaction of skin is classified as H2 criterion, and it will have a score of 2.

Anyway, this additive can still be considered for compounding; however, its selection implies a subsequent specific risk management strategy.

Figure 7 – Additive 8 score system

ii. Upstream & Downstream Chemicals

H1 Criterion

All chemicals used in WP1 met the H1 criterion except CETBIO Reactant 4 and **CETEC Solvent 1**. Both chemicals were found as positive for Reproductive Toxicity. These cases are addressed in detail below.

No conclusive cancer or genotoxicity tests were found as positive for the chemical inventory in the COMPTOX database. In addition, no evidence was found for these compounds from other databases in ECHA's repository.

Therefore, most of chemicals can be considered for the subsequent scale-up, considering their specific Risk Management Measures (RMM). Anyway, in the following section we will assess the safety profile for each individual compound.

Score-system profile

Considering safety score-system is based on endpoints from CLP inventory, we will use CLP harmonized classification, CLP notifications provided by companies and REACH registration to evaluate the current hazards of the proposed additives to generate a complete safety profile. For more information about the score-system and, specifically, safety implementation, you can read again Chapter 1: Introduction.

Table 9 - Summary of WP2 chemical profile

	Acute Tox	Repr. Tox	STOT-SE	STOT-SE	Aspiration Tox	Skin Corrosion	Skin Irritation	Eye Dm/ Eye Irr	Resp/Skin Sens.	Mutagenicity	Carcinogenicity	Aquatic Env.	Ozone Layer	Persistence
CETBIO Buffer 1	3	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
CETBIO Buffer 2	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4
CETBIO Reactant 1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
CETBIO Reactant 2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4
CETBIO Reactant 3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
CETBIO Reactant 4	4	1	3	2	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4
CETBIO Reactant 5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
CETBIO Reactant 6	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
CETBIO Reactant 7	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4

CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4
CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 4	3	4	4	4	4	3	3	3	2	4	4	4	4	4
CETEC Solvent 1	4	1	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4
IRIS Additive 1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
IRIS Buffer 1	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4
IRIS Buffer 2	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4
IRIS Solvent 1	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	4	4	4	2	4	4
IRIS Solvent 2	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4
PHBV (Final Product)	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4

As it has been explained before, for those substances with a score 4 in every column, we can assume that they are not present on the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulation. In addition, according to most notifications provided by companies to ECHA in REACH registrations and CLP notifications, no hazards have been classified. Therefore, we can tentatively consider them as safe additives with a score equal to 4 in all endpoints.

In the following paragraphs, we analyse in detailed the rest of substances with, at least, an endpoint which has been assign with a certain hazard.

CETBIO Buffer 1 (Figure 8)

CETBIO Buffer 1 is on the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulations because it causes severe skin burns (H314) and is toxic if swallowed (H331). In addition, a high number of companies notify that this substance may cause respiratory irritation (H335)

All these endpoints are collected in H3 criteria and will be scored as 3.

Figure 8 – CETBIO Buffer 1 score system

CETBIO Buffer 2 (Figure 9)

According to the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulations CETBIO Buffer 2 causes severe skin burns (H314) and harmful if swallowed (H302). In addition, a high number of companies notify that this substance cause eye damage (H319).

Skin Corrosion, Acute Toxicity and Eye Damage are endpoint within the group of H3-criteria and therefore, they would be classified as Level 2 with a score of 3.

Figure 9 – CETBIO Buffer 2 score system

CETBIO Reactant 2 (Figure 10)

CETBIO Reactant 2 is not on the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulations.

However, according to the classification provided by the majority of companies in CLP notifications, this substance causes serious eye irritation (H319).

Eye irritation is classified in H3 Criteria and, therefore, it would be classified as Level 2 and its score is 3.

Figure 10 – CETBIO Reactant 2 score system

CETBIO Reactant 4 (Figure 11)

CETBIO Reactant 4 is not on the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulations. However, according to the classification provided by companies to ECHA in REACH registrations this substance is suspected of damaging fertility or the unborn child (H360), may cause damage to organs through prolonged or repeated exposure (H373) and may cause drowsiness or dizziness (H363).

Figure 11 - CETBIO Reactant 4 score system

In addition, classification provided by companies to ECHA in CLP notifications identifies that this substance causes serious eye irritation (H319).

Eye irritation and STOT-SE (Cat.3) are included in H3 Criteria, STOT-RE (Cat. 2) are assessed as H2 Criteria and, finally, Reproductive Developmental Toxicity (Cat. 1B) are evaluated as H1 criterion. This last endpoint does not pass the cut-off criterion, and we could consider it a chemical of concern. Reproductive Developmental Toxicity is notified as one of the main hazards for CETBIO Reactant 4 in the majority REACH registration dossiers. Since we do not have access to the Safety Datasheet of the commercial product purchased by CETBIO, we cautiously consider it as a chemical of concern and apply a risk management strategy (see Chapter 5: Conclusions) according to that decision.

CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 3 (Figure 12)

According to the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulations CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 3 causes serious eye damage (H319) and is harmful if swallowed (H302).

Eye irritation (Cat.2) and Acute Toxicity (Cat.4) are classified in H3 Criteria and, therefore, they would be classified as Level 2 and their score is 3.

Figure 12 - CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 3 score system

CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 4 (Figure 13)

CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 4 is not on the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulations

According to the classification provided by companies to ECHA in REACH registrations this substance is harmful if swallowed (H302), causes serious eye damage (H318), causes skin irritation (H315) and may cause an allergic skin reaction (H317). Additionally, the classification provided by companies to ECHA in CLP notifications identifies that this substance causes severe skin burns (H315).

Figure 13 - CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 4 score system

Acute Toxicity (Cat. 4), Skin Corrosion/Irritation and Eye Damage are part of the H3 criterion with a score of 3, but Skin Sensitization is part of the H2 Criterion and, therefore, a score of 2.

CETEC Solvent 1 (Figure 14)

A high number of companies notify that this substance cause eye irritation (H319) with a score equal to 3. However, according to the classification provided by companies to ECHA in REACH registrations this substance is suspected of damaging fertility or the unborn child (H360). This last endpoint will be assessed in H1 Criterion, and it would not pass the cut-off criteria

Safety datasheet purchased by CETEC confirms the Eye Irritation and the Reproductive toxicity endpoints. Therefore, we must treat this substance as a Chemical of concern (see Chapter 5: Conclusions).

Figure 14 – CETEC Solvent 1 score system

IRIS Buffer 1 (Figure 15)

IRIS Buffer 1 is on the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulations because it causes severe skin burns (H314). In addition, a high number of companies notify that this substance cause eye irritation (H319).

Skin Corrosion and Eye Damage are endpoints within the group of H3-criteria and therefore, they would be classified as Level 2 with a score of 3.

These hazards are registered as well in the safety datasheet used by IRIS.

Figure 15 – IRIS Buffer 1 score system

IRIS Buffer 2 (Figure 16)

IRIS Buffer 2 is on the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulations because it is very toxic to aquatic life (H400) and fatal if it is inhaled (H330). Both endpoints are classified as part of the H3 criterion and will be scored with a value of 3.

Safety datasheet confirms these hazards.

IRIS Solvent 1 (Figure 17)

IRIS Solvent 1 is not on the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulations.

However, according to the classification provided by most of the companies in CLP notifications, this substance causes skin irritation (H315), serious eye damage (H318) and is harmful to aquatic life with long lasting effects (H412).

Serious Eye Damage is confirmed in the safety datasheet of the product purchased by IRIS. Eye damage and Skin irritation are classified in H3 Criteria, and it would be classified as Level 2 and with a score of 3, but Chronic Aquatic Toxicity is classified as H2 criteria and, therefore, Level 1 which is scored with 2.

Figure 17 – IRIS Solvent 1 score system

IRIS Solvent 2 (Figure 18)

IRIS Solvent 2 is not on the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulations. According to most notifications provided by companies to ECHA in CLP notifications, it causes skin irritation (H315) and eye irritation (H319). Both endpoints are classified as part of the H3 criterion and will be scored with a value of 3. These hazards are confirmed by the safety datasheet of the commercial product purchased by IRIS.

Figure 18 – IRIS Solvent 2 score system

PHBV (Final Product)

PHBV does not appear in the list of harmonized entries in Annex VI to the CLP Regulations, nor in the notifications provided by companies to ECHA in REACH registrations and CLP notifications. Furthermore, according to CETEC biotechnology safety datasheet, they are not aware of any toxicology data. **Therefore, there is enough evidence about the inherent safety of PHBV.** However, taking into consideration that PHVB is the final product of the product, a more exhaustive investigation will take place. In the following deliverables, additional studies will be undertaken: (1) Scientific review for safety of PHVB beyond safety databases will be carried out to find any evidence of potential toxicity of PHVB materials; (2) potential hazards in the final product related to NIAS will be explored with the development of predictive models; and (3) associated risks regarding production, processing and application of PHBV will be addressed within steps 2 & 3 of the SSbD Framework in the next deliverables.

b. Toxicity prediction of NIAS

According to the GA, IDE will develop the QSAR based tools aimed to model and assess the potential toxicity and side effects of the NIAS after their detection and quantification from CETEC.

NIAS will be studied once they start to be transformed by thermoforming, film extrusion and melt spinning (*Subtask 3.2.2: Compounding*). This study is currently in a preliminary phase, and the first formulations will be ready in a few months.

For NIAS characterization by chromatography, a complete study of potential metals, volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and semi-volatile organic compounds (SVOCs) will be performed. Both SVOCs and VOCs are expected to be created by thermal degradation of PHBV and additives, however, a general study will be done for these classes and not only for expected degradation products. This is a preventive measure, because some additional additive could have been added to commercial polymers used for the mixtures.

Meanwhile, IDENER has been working on a strategy for toxicity prediction in order to address the whole chemical profile of potential NIAS formed by thermal degradation.

i. Endpoint definition

Related to endpoint definition for safety assessment in Deliverable 6.3, a multi-integrated model was proposed to predict the chemical profile, and their subsequent classification of NIAS produced within the project. A list of models with different endpoints will be developed with a shared applicability domain: Degradation products -(semi)volatile organic compounds- from compounding activities with PHBV.

The selected endpoint should define the potential hazards (not only for intrinsic properties, but also for subsequent hazard of workers safety or environmental exposure) with the minimum number of points. However, they must cover (1) Potential toxicity and side effects of the NIAS; (2) Favourable conditions for production of NIAS with negative effects; (3) Required parameters not experimentally available for potential hazards for workers; and (4) Physicochemical characteristics of the materials required as input if they are not experimentally available for consumer exposure.

In order to reduce the high number of available endpoints, hazards will be focused on the production process. Specifically, since NIAS are expected to appear in the compounding phase because the higher temperatures, and those substances to be evaluated will be characterized as VOCs or SVOCs, all endpoints will assess hazards related to phase gas compounds, occupational exposure and air contamination.

The following list contains the enumerated hazards of the models:

- Carcinogenic
- Acute Toxicity (Inhalation)
- Acute Toxicity (Oral)
- Aspiration hazard
- Skin Sensitization
- Air-Blood absorption
- Biodegradability

Acute toxicity will be evaluated for inhalation (related to the production process) and oral exposure (pertaining to end-of-life and release processes). Additionally, aspiration hazards will be considered. For dermal exposure, predictions will focus on skin sensitization. Carcinogenicity will also be assessed to address cut-off criteria throughout the product's entire life cycle. Moreover, biodegradability will be calculated to extend the assessment of toxicity into the environmental domain.

Furthermore, an air-blood absorption model will be implemented to correlate carcinogenic toxicity from inhalation exposure with the potential distribution of chemicals to organs, accounting for the exchange of substances between blood and air in the lungs.

ii. Databases

Chemical information to create new predictive toxicity models has been obtained from eChemPortal. eChemPortal allows simultaneous searching of reports and datasets by chemical name and number, by chemical property, and by GHS classification. Direct links to collections of chemical hazard and risk information prepared for government chemical programs at national, regional and international levels are obtained. Classification results according to national/regional hazard classification schemes or to the Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS) are provided when available. In addition, eChemPortal provides also exposure and use information on chemicals.^x

eChemPortal allows to search on chemical properties and effects: physical and chemical properties, environmental fate and pathways, ecotoxicological and toxicological information. Therefore, some OECD TG were selected as guidelines to harmonize results and ensure a minimum quality on the comparison of results. The OECD *Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals* is a collection of about 150 of the most relevant internationally agreed testing methods used by government, industry and independent laboratories to identify and characterize potential hazards of chemicals. They are a set of tools for professionals, used primarily in regulatory safety testing and subsequent chemical and chemical product notification, chemical registration and in chemical evaluation. They can also be used for the selection and ranking of candidate chemicals during the development of new chemicals and products and in toxicological research.

The chosen OECD TG were:

- a) Test No. 114: Viscosity of Liquids^{xi}
- b) Test No. 301d: Ready Biodegradability^{xii}
- c) Test No. 403: Acute Inhalation Toxicity^{xiii}
- d) Test No. 406: Skin Sensitisation (in vivo non-LLNA)^{xiv}
- e) Test No. 423: Acute Oral toxicity - Acute Toxic Class Method^{xv}
- f) Test No. 429: Skin Sensitisation (in vivo LLNA)^{xvi}
- g) Test No. 451: Carcinogenicity Studies^{xvii}

iii. Applicability domain

The goal of the toxicity prediction is to develop a model for generated VOCs and SVOCs in the compounding of PHBV which could be used, not only for toxicity prediction of NIAS within ViSS project, but also for any development of PHBV. Therefore, we have defined the chemical space of the model regarding the chemical structure of PHBV, their degradation products, the additives and (S)VOCs in general. Similarity with these structures will be a mandatory criterion to create the database for the training set of the model.

Three databases were used as reference for designing the chemical space.

- WP1 additives (9 compounds)
- Degradation of products extracted from literature (9 compounds)
- (S)VOCs from literature (440 compounds)

First, atoms from reference databases were collected and summarized. Then, all datasets from OECD TG were filtered according to these atoms and every chemical with an atom which is not part of the list was deleted.

Second, the new filtered-by-atom datasets were compared to reference databases using MACCS Keys Fingerprints. MACCS keys are 166-bit 2D structure fingerprints that are commonly used for the measure of molecular similarity^{xviii}. A similarity matrix was developed comparing OECD TG datasets (y axis) with reference databases (x axis). For each chemical of every dataset, maximum similarity and mean similarity were calculated for the comparison with (S)VOC databases.

Finally, after analysing the similarity results, the criteria for selecting the compounds to define the chemical space were a threshold value of 0.5 for maximum similarity. The explanation behind this decision is trying to replicate a chemical space for (S)VOC, finding a point for every compound in the chemical space, at least at 0.5 for MACCS keys.

	OECD TG	eChemPortal Compounds	Atom Filter	Unique Values	Similarity Threshold
0	114	399	354	317	262
1	301d	746	558	506	372
2	403	733	378	321	206
3	406	1999	1169	768	516
4	423	1467	868	804	477
5	429	1867	1226	1076	646
6	451	92	71	50	21

Table 10 - Number of compounds for every dataset in each step

Table 10 summarizes the filtering process until the final size of the dataset to build the chemical space for each OECD TG. After that, the chemical space of the final model will be optimized in the next steps (elimination of outliers in the clustering and application of predictive algorithms).

As can be observed in Table 10, the final size of OECD TG 451 is not enough to ensure a good model. Therefore, new databases must be found in the next steps

5. Next steps

a. Safety Assessment

During the next months, occupational and environmental exposure will be studied in detail through computational tools. A risk assessment strategy will be implemented by steps 2 & 3 of the SSbD Framework. For this, we will combine exposure results with hazard profile we already have.

Regarding the SSbD Assessment for the rest of WPs our contribution for exposure assessment and the development of a Risk management plan (WP2), the exposure assessment of compound transformation (WP3), and the definition of risk reduction measures for implementation in Demo-plant (WP4) is expected to be included in the D6.9.

By the other side, risk assessment related to End-Of-Life (WP4) will be included in the last deliverable (D6.14), together with Risk Assessment based on scale-up dimensions and the input for eco-design of the packaging demonstrators (WP5).

b. Toxicity prediction of NIAS

The final goal for toxicity prediction of NIAS is to develop a set of computational models to predict some endpoints related to Human Health and Environmental Safety. Three steps have been already done (and described in Results section: Endpoint definition, Applicability Domain and Databases download).

Next step is to apply machine learning algorithms to establish mathematical relationships between the chemical structure of chemicals in the same chemical space of interest (SVOCs and VOCs) and their toxicity according to different tests. From these relationships we will be able to develop a set of computational models to predict each of the selected endpoints.

These steps will be detailed in the next deliverable (D6.9).

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6. Conclusions

A safety assessment of intrinsic properties has been performed for commercial compounds of a list of potential additives for compounding and chemicals employed in WP2. As a main conclusion, all the additives have passed the H1 criteria and, therefore, they can be used in the next step (compounding) and two chemicals have been detected as suspected of being positives for H1 criteria endpoints: CETBIO Reactant 4 and CETEC Solvent 1.

However, a more exhaustive analysis has been performed consulting the CLP harmonized classification, CLP notifications provided by companies and REACH registration to evaluate the criteria H2 and H3, describing the whole safety profile and giving a safety score individually for each compound, thus, a comparison can be made between additives. In addition, chemical profiles will help with the next steps of SSbD assessment for risk management.

In the case of WP1 assessment, those additives which have a safer profile should be considered as the chosen one. In this case, only Additive 5 and Additive 8 have worse safety profiles. However, if Additives 5 & 8 present the best technical profile, they might be considered as well, but a specific risk management strategy must be applied.

For CETBIO Reactant 4 and CETEC Solvent 1 should be prioritized for substitution. However, if they have not an ideal substitute and they are considered as essential for society we can safely use them, controlling their emissions along the whole life cycle while activities are undertaken to develop alternatives as soon as possible and their use is phased out as soon as less hazardous alternatives are available, as well as tracking them through their life cycle.

For those chemicals which present some endpoints with a score lower than 4 but higher than 1, they might be still considered, because they pass the cut-off criteria, but a specific risk management strategy must be applied in the demo-plant stage. Especially, once we consider occupational and environmental exposure.

On the other hand, the development of new predictive models for calculating potential toxicity of NIAS (degradation products for thermosetting and end-of-life process) is in a good phase and the compilation of databases, filtering and description of the chemical space is already done (except for carcinogenicity). Therefore, the development of the QSAR models is on time.

ANNEX 1 - Questionnaires

In this Annex, inventory template and Questionnaires about safety measures and operational conditions will be shown. In order to maintain the confidentiality of the chemicals employed in industrial processes by companies, broader terms are still being used. CAS Numbers, providers and links to the SDS have been also removed from the inventory to keep confidentiality.

These surveys are the first contact with industrial partners, after that, an iterative process for solving doubts, fixing potential mistakes and filling gaps has been conducted via mail. For that reason, it is important to remember that the information included below is only the first step of the SSbD assessment of an iterative and long process.

It is important to remark that in the deliverable, although chemicals have been clustered by company, some of them are used by more than one partner. Therefore, we can refer to a chemical of a certain company with the key name of another company, just to avoid unnecessary replication of data.

a. Questionnaire – CETEC

1. Monitoring and Control of Alkaline Hydrolysis:

- Describe your procedures for monitoring and controlling critical parameters (e.g., temperature, pH, reaction time) during the alkaline hydrolysis process to ensure efficient nutrient extraction and prevent unintended reactions.

Critical parameter of alkaline hydrolysis are temperature and concentration of the alkaline species (caustic soda). Temperature is monitored with a thermometer and pH with an electronic pH meter.

- What methods will you use to monitor the progress of the hydrolysis reaction and ensure completion?

Completion of the reaction is controlled by analysis of the N and P content in the liquid fraction of the bones and feathers hydrolysis.

2. Safety Protocols During Alkaline Hydrolysis:

- How will you ensure the safe handling and storage of concentrated **IRIS BUFFER 1** solution?
IRIS BUFFER 1 solution must be storage in a cool, well-ventilated area away from water and moisture. IRIS BUFFER 1 also reacts with metals and can attack plastic, rubbers and coating. It should be stored in the original container and locked up. All laboratory personnel must understand certain basic principles of toxicology and recognize the major classes of toxic and corrosive chemicals. General personal protective equipment (PPE) is mandatory.
- Describe the personal protective equipment (PPE) required for personnel working with **IRIS BUFFER 1** solution and potentially hazardous biological materials (cell debris, BFH).
Safety glasses with side shields, long sleeved laboratory coats, chemically resistant gloves, and closed toed shoes should be worn when handling small quantities of weak or dilute acids and bases. This is to be considered as minimum protection and must be upgraded if necessary. Additional PPEs such as chemical goggles, face-shield, chemical apron, disposable coveralls, and

respiratory protection should be worn if there is a greater chance of chemical exposure or when handling strong or concentrated acids or bases.

- What procedures are in place to manage spills or leaks of **IRIS BUFFER 1** solution?
For Sodium Hydroxide in solution absorb liquids in dry sand, earth, or a similar material and place into sealed containers for disposal. If solid, collect solid material in the most convenient and safe manner and place into sealed containers for disposal. PPE must be used.
- How will you control and monitor potential exposure to hazardous fumes or aerosols generated during the hydrolysis process?
Conducting all procedures involving volatile toxic substances and operations involving solid or liquid toxic substances that may result in the generation of aerosols in a laboratory chemical hood.
- Outline your emergency response procedures in case of accidents or injuries involving **IRIS BUFFER 1** or biological materials.
Eye contact: quickly brush off excess chemical from the face. Flush with a large amount of water lifting upper and lower lids. Remove contact lenses if worn, while flushing. Seek medical attention immediately.
Skin contact: quickly remove contaminated clothing. Blot or brush off excess chemical and wash gently with large amount of water. Seek medical attention immediately.
Inhalation: remove the person from exposure. Begin rescue breathing and RCP using universal precautions if breathing or heart action has stop. Transfer promptly to a medical facility.

3. Worker Exposure:

- How is exposure to hazardous chemicals controlled to prevent health risks to lab personnel?
There are not hazardous chemicals used during the synthesis and extraction of PHBV, nevertheless, there are basic precautions to avoid exposure by principal routes (contact with skin and eyes, inhalation and ingestion).
 - *Engineering controls that eliminate, isolate or reduce exposure to chemical or physical hazards through laboratory chemical hoods and other ventilation systems. Also conduct all procedures involving substances that may result in the generation of aerosols in a laboratory chemical hood.*
 - *Eye protection is required for all personnel in all locations where laboratory chemicals are stored or used, whether or not one is actually performing a chemical operation. Safety glasses with side shields provide the minimum protection acceptable for regular use.*
 - *Eating, drinking, smoking, gum chewing, applying cosmetics, and taking medicine in laboratories where hazardous chemicals are used or stored should be strictly prohibited. Food, beverages, cups, and other drinking and eating utensils should not be stored in areas where hazardous chemicals are handled or stored.*
- What types of personal protective equipment are required for personnel handling these chemicals?
Safety glasses with side shields, long sleeved laboratory coats, chemically resistant gloves, and closed toed shoes. Additional PPEs such as chemical goggles, face-shield, chemical apron,

disposable coveralls, and respiratory protection should be worn if there is a greater chance of chemical exposure.

- What ventilation systems are in place, and how are spills of hazardous materials managed?
Ventilation system in place are laboratory chemical hoods. When a chemical spill occurs, it is important to control the source of the spill, take immediate steps to stop the leakage or control the spill. Second, contain the spill. Liquid spills will be contained by spreading absorbent material. In case of reactor breakage or leak, there is a containment bucket below.

b. Questionnaire – CETBIO

1. Control of Fermentation Conditions:

- Describe your procedures for monitoring and controlling critical parameters (time, temperature, pH, salinity, agitation) during the fermentation process to ensure optimal biomass growth and PHBV production.

The fermentation is automatically controlled by a PID controller that records everything during the process, including the initial and final time. With this system, a setpoint is defined for temperature, pH and dissolved oxygen controlled by the agitation and the aeration. These parameters are measured with their respective probes, which a continuous reading of the values against the setpoint values. When a deviation from the setpoint values occurs, the system adjusts the parameters by adding a base or an acid to regulate the pH, increasing the heating or cooling to suit the temperature, or increasing the agitation and/or the aeration to maintain the dissolved oxygen.

2. Proliferation Control:

- What strategies will you implement to control the growth of unwanted bacterial species that may decrease fermentation yield or produce toxic byproducts?

During the fermentation, biomass growth is monitored by absorbance, dry cell weight and count plate, and by microscopy to ensure the absence of contamination. Strategies to avoid contamination are to always use fresh inoculum with high cell concentration to reduce the possibility of contamination and, if contamination occurs, to terminate the fermentation and clean all the contaminated equipment and places.

3. Waste Stream Analysis:

- Describe your methods for analysing the composition of waste streams (brine, water) generated during the fermentation process to ensure their suitability for reuse in the broth.

The water and brine are analyzed by conductimetry and ionic chromatography.

4. AcOEt Disposal:

- How will you safely dispose of or potentially reuse the green solvent AcOEt (ethyl acetate) after the liquid-liquid extraction of PHBV?

AcOEt is no longer going to be use for the extraction.

5. Safety Protocols:

- Describe the safety protocols for handling biological materials (Hfx. mediterranei, cell debris, poultry residues) during fermentation and biomass growth.

The microorganism used is non-hazardous, so the safety protocol for its application is standard. The preparation of the inocula is carried out in sterility, using gloves and coat, but the manipulation of the biomass during the fermentation or cell debris doesn't need any particular protection. For the poultry residues, as they have been pretreated and we receive a milled and frozen material, the manipulation is also standard.

- What personal protective equipment (PPE) will be required for personnel working with these materials?

The required PPE are glove, overall or lab coat and security glasses and shoes.

- Outline your emergency response procedures in case of accidents or spills involving biological materials or AcOEt.

As the level of biohazard is low, they can be sweep away or wash.

6. Worker Exposure:

- How is exposure to hazardous chemicals controlled to prevent health risks to lab personnel?
All volatile compounds are treated under an extraction cabinet.

- What types of personal protective equipment are required for personnel handling these chemicals?

The required PPE are glove, overall or lab coat, face mask, security glasses and security shoes.

- What ventilation systems are in place, and how are spills of hazardous materials managed?
All hazardous materials are treated in an extraction cabinet.

c. Questionnaire – IRIS

1. Waste Liquor Handling:

- What procedures do you have for safe handling and monitoring of the candy sugar-rich liquor waste during storage and transfer?

To ensure safe handling and monitoring of the sugar-rich liquor waste, we have implemented the following procedures:

- Collection and Transportation: *The waste is collected by VIDAL using approved containers and transported under controlled conditions at freezing temperatures.*
- Storage at IRIS: *Upon arrival at IRIS, the waste is immediately stored in designated freezer units at -18°C or colder. Storage containers are sealed and labelled to prevent contamination.*
- Monitoring and Documentation: *Temperature and pH levels are checked at the reception and before using the waste using calibrated instruments.*
- Safety Measures: *All personnel handling the waste are required to wear appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE), including gloves, lab coats, and safety glasses.*
- Utilization: *The waste is half-thawed and processed for utilization according to our established protocols.*

- How will you ensure consistent waste liquor composition for the fermentation process?

To ensure consistent waste liquor composition for the fermentation process, we will implement the following strategies:

- Standardization of Production: We will work closely with VIDAL to establish standardized production practices that minimize fluctuations in the sugar-rich liquor composition. This may involve adjusting production schedules or using more consistent raw materials.
- Regular Sampling and Analysis: Samples of the waste liquor will be collected at regular intervals and analysed in an external laboratory to determine their chemical composition. This data will be used to identify trends and potential sources of variation.
- Adjustment: If necessary, we will adjust the composition of the batch to achieve a more consistent feedstock for the fermentation process.
- Process Control: We will implement real-time process monitoring and control systems to monitor the fermentation process and make adjustments as needed to optimize VFA yield and product quality.

2. Risk Management for Specific Chemicals:

- How are risks associated with strong acid/base agents managed in the laboratory, particularly during the residue conditioning process?

To manage the risks associated with strong acid/base agents, particularly during the residue conditioning process, we have implemented the following safety measures:

- Safe Storage: **IRIS BUFFER 1** and **IRIS BUFFER 2** are stored in designated, secure areas, away from incompatible materials. Containers are clearly labelled and properly sealed. Preparation and handling of the reagents must be done inside the fume hood.
- Personal Protective Equipment (PPE): All personnel handling these chemicals are required to wear appropriate PPE, including lab coats, gloves, safety glasses, and respiratory protection as needed.
- Ventilation: The laboratory is equipped with adequate ventilation to ensure proper air quality and minimize exposure to hazardous fumes.
- Training: All laboratory personnel receive regular training on the safe handling, storage, and disposal of strong acids and bases.

3. Extraction Solvents:

- What specific green solvents do you plan to use for VFA extraction and what are their associated safety hazards?

*We plan to use a deep eutectic solvent (DES) composed of **IRIS SOLVENT 1** and **IRIS SOLVENT 2** for VFA extraction. While these solvents are considered greener alternatives to traditional organic solvents, it's important to be aware of their potential safety hazards:*

- Skin irritation: May cause skin irritation, especially in sensitive individuals.
- Eye irritation: Can cause eye irritation if it comes into contact with the eyes.
- Ingestion: Ingestion may cause gastrointestinal upset.

To minimize risks associated with these solvents, we will implement the following safety measures:

- Wear appropriate PPE: Personnel handling these solvents will wear gloves, eye protection, and lab coats.
- Avoid skin and eye contact: Handle solvents with care to prevent direct contact.
- Work in a well-ventilated area: Ensure adequate ventilation to reduce exposure to fumes.
- Store properly: Store solvents in labelled containers in a secure location.

- Describe your plan for safe disposal or potential reuse of spent extraction solvents, considering environmental regulations.

To comply with Spanish environmental regulations and ensure responsible management of spent extraction solvents, we will implement the following plan:

- Solvent Recovery: *We will explore options for recovering and reusing spent d-menthol and lauric acid. This may include: Distillation and Recycling.*
- Waste Management: *If recovery is not possible, the spent solvents will be disposed of in accordance with Spanish waste management regulations. This may involve: Hazardous waste classification according to the Spanish regulations, then hazardous waste will be transported and disposed of by licensed waste management companies.*

By following this plan, we aim to minimize environmental impact, promote sustainable practices, and comply with all applicable Spanish regulations regarding the management of spent extraction solvents.

4. Green Solvent Recovery:

- If applicable, what methods will you use to recover and reuse the green solvents used in the extraction process?

Solvent Recovery: We will explore options for recovering the spent IRIS SOLVENT 1 and IRIS SOLVENT 2. This may include: Distillation.

- Explain any safety considerations associated with your chosen solvent recovery methods.

Distillation involves handling volatile substances that can pose significant safety risks. To ensure a safe working environment, it is crucial to address the following safety considerations:

- Fire and Explosion Hazards: *Many solvents produce flammable vapours that can ignite or create explosive mixtures. Prevent ignition sources near the distillation apparatus and ensure adequate ventilation.*
- Chemical Exposure: *Solvent vapours can be inhaled, leading to respiratory irritation. Avoid direct skin and eye contact by wearing appropriate protective equipment.*
- Heat-Related Hazards: *Distillation equipment can become very hot, posing burn risks. Use heat-resistant gloves and avoid touching hot surfaces.*
- Equipment Failure: *Glass breakage or equipment malfunctions can lead to leaks or spills. Use safety shields and maintain equipment regularly.*
- Emergency Preparedness: *Have a spill response plan in place, provide first aid training, and ensure a well-stocked first aid kit.*

5. By-Product Analysis and Utilization:

- What methods will you use to analyse the composition of water and biomass by-products from the VFA production process?

The propionic acid content will be determined by HPLC, and the biomass production will be determined by spectrophotometric and gravimetric methods. By-product analysis will not be conducted.

- How will you handle and potentially utilize the water and biomass by-products, considering contamination and waste disposal?

To handle the water and biomass by-products while minimizing contamination and waste disposal, we will implement a Sterilization step (124 °C, 24 min) to ensure the destruction of any harmful microorganisms.

6. Waste Disposal and Environmental Protection:

- What intentionally added substances were used during material processing?

The following substances were added to improve the fermentation process:

- IRIS Additive 1
- IRIS Buffer 1
- IRIS Buffer 2
- IRIS Solvent 2
- Peptone
- Yeast

- Were non-intentionally added substances detected during the manufacturing process? If so, how were they experimentally isolated and what was their estimated concentration?

No non-intentionally added substances were detected during the manufacturing process.

- How are by-products managed and disposed of?

To handle the water and biomass by-products while minimizing contamination and waste disposal, we will implement a Sterilization step (124 °C, 24 min) to ensure the destruction of any harmful microorganisms. The sterilized and inactivated residue will be disposed of following the laboratory's protocols for the disposal of biological waste.

- What procedures are in place for the safe handling and neutralization of these residues?

The procedures for the safe handling and neutralization of these residues are as follows include:

- Wearing Personal Protective Equipment
- Handling residues with care avoiding spills or contact with skin or mucous membranes.
- Sterilizing at 124 °C during 24 min.
- Disposing the sterilized and inactive residue according to local regulations and guidelines for biological waste disposal.

- What procedures are followed for the disposal of chemical wastes, including unreacted compound, solvents, and other reactants?

IRIS has established a procedure for the disposal of chemical wastes, including unreacted compounds, solvents, and other reactants, in compliance with Spanish legislation. A local company, contracted by IRIS, collects the chemical wastes at regular intervals. This company is authorized to handle and transport hazardous materials. The disposal of the treated wastes is carried out in accordance with Spanish environmental regulations.

7. Worker Exposure:

- How is exposure to hazardous chemicals controlled to prevent health risks to lab personnel?

To prevent health risks to laboratory personnel, IRIS has implemented the following measures:

- Regular risk assessments are conducted to identify potential hazards associated with the use of hazardous chemicals.
- Appropriate PPE is provided and required for laboratory personnel when working with hazardous chemicals. This includes gloves, lab coats, safety glasses, respiratory protection, and other necessary equipment.

- Training programs are provided to educate laboratory personnel on the proper use of PPE, emergency procedures, and other safety measures.
- Access to the laboratory is restricted to authorized personnel.
- What types of personal protective equipment are required for personnel handling these chemicals?

Personal protective equipment includes gloves, lab coats, safety glasses, respiratory protection, and other necessary equipment.

- What ventilation systems are in place, and how are spills of hazardous materials managed?

Ventilation Systems

- Fume hoods: These are enclosures designed to capture and exhaust hazardous fumes away from the laboratory. They are equipped with variable airflow controls to adjust ventilation based on the specific chemicals being used.
- General ventilation: The laboratory is equipped with a general ventilation system to ensure adequate air exchange and dilution of airborne contaminants.

Spill contamination

- In case of a spill, personnel are trained to respond promptly by isolating the area, evacuating if necessary, and preventing the spread of the spill. Emergency spill kits are readily available in the laboratory, containing absorbent materials, neutralizers, and other necessary equipment for containment and cleanup.

d. Chemical Inventory (All)

<i>Name</i>	<i>Processes related</i>	<i>Step</i>
CETBIO		
<i>CETBIO Buffer 1</i>	<i>The chemical/material is intentionally added as a component in a mixture/formulation process</i>	<i>Fermentative processes to growth the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range</i>
<i>CETBIO Buffer 2</i>	<i>The chemical/material is intentionally added as a component in a mixture/formulation process</i>	<i>Fermentative processes to growth the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 1</i>	<i>The chemical/material is intentionally added as a component in a mixture/formulation process</i>	<i>Fermentative processes to growth the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 2</i>	<i>The chemical/material is intentionally added as a component in a mixture/formulation process</i>	<i>Fermentative processes to growth the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 3</i>	<i>The chemical/material is intentionally added as a component in a mixture/formulation process</i>	<i>Fermentative processes to growth the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 4</i>	<i>The chemical/material is intentionally added as a component in a mixture/formulation process</i>	<i>Fermentative processes to growth the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 5</i>	<i>The chemical/material is intentionally added as a component in a mixture/formulation process</i>	<i>Fermentative processes to growth the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 6</i>	<i>The chemical/material is intentionally added as a component in a mixture/formulation process</i>	<i>Fermentative processes to growth the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range</i>
<i>CETBIO Reactant 7</i>	<i>The chemical/material is intentionally added as a component in a mixture/formulation process</i>	<i>Fermentative processes to growth the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range</i>
<i>CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 1</i>	<i>The chemical/material is consumed or used for chemical processing to be transformed into another</i>	<i>Fermentative processes to growth the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range</i>
<i>CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 2</i>	<i>The chemical/material is consumed or used for chemical processing to be transformed into another</i>	<i>Fermentative processes to growth the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range</i>

<i>CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 3</i>	<i>The chemical/material is consumed or used for chemical processing to be transformed into another</i>	<i>Fermentative processes to grow the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range</i>
<i>CETBIO Culture Media Ingredient 4</i>	<i>The chemical/material is consumed or used for chemical processing to be transformed into another</i>	<i>Fermentative processes to grow the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range</i>
<i>PHBV (Final Product)</i>	<i>Final Product</i>	<i>Final Product</i>
CETEC		
<i>CETEC Solvent 1</i>	<i>The chemical/material is used in the manufacturing of a product and is not meant to be part of the final product</i>	<i>Downstream processes to achieve high recovery efficacy and PHBV purity</i>
<i>PHBV (Final Product)</i>	<i>Final Product</i>	<i>Final Product</i>
IRIS		
<i>IRIS Additive 1</i>	<i>The chemical/material is intentionally added as a component in a mixture/formulation process</i>	<i>The chemical/material is intentionally added as a component in a mixture/formulation process</i>
<i>IRIS Buffer 1</i>	<i>The chemical/material is used in the manufacturing of a product and is not meant to be part of the final product</i>	<i>The chemical/material is used in the manufacturing of a product and is not meant to be part of the final product</i>
<i>IRIS Buffer 2</i>	<i>The chemical/material is used in the manufacturing of a product and is not meant to be part of the final product</i>	<i>The chemical/material is used in the manufacturing of a product and is not meant to be part of the final product</i>
<i>IRIS Solvent 1</i>	<i>The chemical/material is used in the manufacturing of a product and is not meant to be part of the final product</i>	<i>Downstream processes to achieve high recovery efficacy and PHBV purity</i>
<i>IRIS Solvent 2</i>	<i>The chemical/material is used in the manufacturing of a product and is not meant to be part of the final product</i>	<i>Downstream processes to achieve high recovery efficacy and PHBV purity</i>

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